

The Influence of Non-Physical Work Environment, Work-Life Balance, and Work Discipline on Employee Turnover Intention: A Quantitative Study of Employees at PT Bhumi Phala Perkasa

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ABSTRACT: Human Resources (HR) play a pivotal role in the success and sustainability of a company amid the ever-evolving business dynamics. Effective HR management can positively impact employee turnover rates. One company experiencing a high rate of turnover intention is PT Bhumi Phala Perkasa. Based on the company's turnover rate data, it was 13.01% in 2020, decreased to 10.98% in 2021, but increased to 13.51% in 2022. In 2023, with data obtained up to September 2023, the turnover rate was 12.77%. Given this phenomenon, this study aims to determine the influence of non-physical work environment, work-life balance, and work discipline on turnover intention. This research phenomenon was explored using a questionnaire method. Data collection was conducted by distributing questionnaires to several employees at the company. The analysis technique used is the SEM-PLS method. The analysis results show that the non-physical work environment, work-life balance, and work discipline have a significant negative impact on turnover intention. This means that the higher the influence of the non-physical work environment, work-life balance, and work discipline, the lower the level of employee turnover intention at PT. Bhumi Phala Perkasa. This research is expected to be useful for company management. The findings of this study can help PT Bhumi Phala Perkasa in efforts to suppress turnover intention through the non-physical work environment, work-life balance, and work discipline. In general, with the results of this research, the organization can understand and identify the needs and desires of employees, which can be used as a consideration and evaluation for the organization comprehensively in formulating human resource management policies in the organization in the future.

KEYWORDS: Turnover Intention, Work Environment, Worklife Balance, Work Discipline.

INTRODUCTION

Human resources (HR) play a vital role in the success and sustainability of companies amid an increasingly dynamic business landscape. Effective HR management is not only a functional responsibility but also a strategic foundation that influences an organization's competitiveness, innovation, and continuity. With high-quality human resources, companies can optimally achieve their mission and vision [1]. However, one significant HR challenge that companies face is managing employee turnover. High turnover rates often indicate inefficient HR management and can lead to substantial financial losses due to recruitment and training expenses for new employees. In this context, PT Bhumi Phala Perkasa has experienced high turnover rates, with figures fluctuating over recent years: 13.01% in 2020, decreasing to 10.98% in 2021, then rising again to 13.51% in 2022, and slightly lowering to 12.77% in 2023. This level of turnover, exceeding 10%, is categorized as high, leading to considerable impact on the company's performance [2].

High turnover can disrupt organizational stability and impede productivity. Identifying factors behind turnover can help PT Bhumi Phala Perkasa design effective strategies to retain talent and prevent the loss of key employees. According to Ardana (in Riani, [3]), human resources are invaluable assets, crucial for an organization's success. Turnover intention—the likelihood of an employee leaving the organization—can predict actual turnover. Organizations must therefore foster a supportive environment to prevent skilled employees from wanting to leave. Robbins and Coulter (in Sismawati, [4]) also highlight that high turnover intentions can burden companies with recruitment and training costs while disrupting workplace dynamics. Studies indicate that turnover is driven by factors like job dissatisfaction, weak organizational commitment, work-life conflict, and perceived workplace injustice [5].

Exit interviews at PT Bhumi Phala Perkasa reveal that employees often leave for better opportunities, indicating dissatisfaction with current roles. This aligns with Sukwadi and Meliana's [6] definition of turnover intention as a tendency to leave for various reasons,

including seeking better positions. Additionally, non-physical work environment factors, such as unclear career advancement and lack of managerial support, have been highlighted by employees. Poor communication from supervisors often leads to conflicts and performance-related misunderstandings, further contributing to turnover. A non-physical work environment encompasses the psychological aspects of workplace relationships, as stated by Setyadi, Utami, & Nurthjahjono [7], who found it to be a key contributor to turnover intention.

Work discipline is another issue impacting turnover at PT Bhumi Phala Perkasa. A disciplined workforce enhances operational stability, while lack of discipline—manifested through absenteeism, unprofessional behavior, and disregard for safety protocols—leads to inefficiency and increased turnover [8]. Observational data shows an average absenteeism rate of 7.144% in 2023, exceeding the company's 5% tolerance level. Disciplinary issues correlate with turnover, as employees with poor discipline often have higher turnover intentions [9]; [10].

Work-life balance (WLB) also affects turnover. WLB refers to managing work and personal life, with imbalances increasing turnover risk. A survey revealed that 63% of employees at PT Bhumi Phala Perkasa have commutes exceeding 10 minutes, often working longer than agreed hours, leading to fatigue and reduced family time. Research indicates that excessive commute times can negatively affect WLB [11]. Studies by Afnisa [12] and Hafid [13] support that poor WLB correlates positively with turnover intention.

1.1. Research Objectives

Based on the previous problem formulation, the objectives of this research are as follows:

- a. To identify and analyze the impact of the non-physical work environment on employee turnover intention at PT Bhumi Phala Perkasa.
- b. To identify and analyze the impact of work-life balance on employee turnover intention at PT Bhumi Phala Perkasa.
- c. To identify and analyze the impact of work discipline on employee turnover intention at PT Bhumi Phala Perkasa.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Non-Physical Work Environment

The non-physical work environment, as described by Sedarmayanti [14] and others, involves situations related to interactions within the workplace, including relationships with superiors, colleagues, and subordinates. This environment is essential for fostering productivity, focusing on creating a harmonious atmosphere and effective communication between team members. Ideal conditions emerge when leaders supervise effectively, mutual trust exists, and there is a supportive, harmonious atmosphere [15]; [16]. In this environment, strong relational aspects between management and staff and among coworkers significantly impact the achievement of company goals through effective communication and teamwork [17]; [7].

B. Work-life Balance

Work-life balance, as explained by Delecta [18], and Robbins and Coulter [19], is the ability to balance work demands with personal and family needs, ensuring comfort in both domains. This balance is supported by company programs offering flexibility in work hours, remote work, and family-friendly benefits. Ricardianto [20] highlights that a balanced work environment can foster harmony between work and personal life, positively impacting productivity. Overall, work-life balance is essential for individuals to comfortably manage both personal and professional commitments, benefiting both areas simultaneously.

C. Work Discipline

Work discipline is essential for achieving optimal performance, as it reflects employees' adherence to company regulations and social norms. Rivai [21] and Hasibuan [22] describe work discipline as a means for managers to encourage behavioral adjustments and enhance employees' awareness and compliance. Singodimedjo [23] emphasize that high discipline among employees accelerates company goals, while low discipline hinders them. Mangkunegara [24] classifies discipline into preventive, which aims to prevent rule violations, and corrective, which imposes sanctions on violators to promote adherence. Indicators of high work discipline include enthusiasm, responsibility, and unity among employees, while low discipline manifests in high absenteeism, tardiness, and reduced motivation.

D. Turnover Intention

Turnover intention refers to an individual's inclination or desire to leave their current job voluntarily. Zeffane, as cited by Bimaputra and Parwoto [25], defines it as the tendency or intention of an individual to resign. View turnover intention as problematic due to its associated recruitment, selection, and training costs, along with disruptions to company workflows. Similarly, Robbins and Juges [26] describe turnover intention as a state in which an employee seeks to leave the organization, while Priansa [27] connects it to job dissatisfaction. Knudsen (in Kartono, [28]) further elaborates it as an employee's behavioral intent to either leave or stay with an organization. Mathis and Jackson [29] associate turnover intention with job satisfaction and organizational commitment, while Sukwadi and Meliana [6] emphasize the role of personal aspirations and the search for better positions as key factors in this decision-making process.

METHOD

This study adopts a quantitative research method, which refers to a structured scientific investigation of elements and phenomena, along with their cause-and-effect relationships. Quantitative research is defined as a systematic analysis of phenomena by gathering measurable data using statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques [30]. The study utilizes both descriptive and causal methods. Descriptive quantitative methods typically focus on measuring the degree of variables within a population or sample, while causal methods examine correlations and relationships between two or more variables. Descriptive analysis is used to explore or describe the social situations being studied in depth, while causal methods evaluate potential cause-and-effect relationships [30]. In this study, there is no researcher intervention in data collection or analysis, as data is gathered directly from respondents. The research focuses on individual aspects, using a cross-sectional method where data is collected at one specific point in time and the research concludes once the data collection is complete [31].

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Validity Test

Table 1. Convergent Validity Test Results through Outer Loading

Variable	Item	Outer Loading	Description
Non-Physical Work Environment	NPWE1	0.784	Valid
	NPWE10	0.791	Valid
	NPWE11	0.795	Valid
	NPWE12	0.768	Valid
	NPWE13	0.785	Valid
	NPWE14	0.799	Valid
	NPWE15	0.798	Valid
	NPWE16	0.795	Valid
	NPWE17	0.827	Valid
	NPWE18	0.791	Valid
	NPWE2	0.808	Valid
	NPWE3	0.788	Valid
	NPWE4	0.740	Valid
	NPWE5	0.768	Valid
	NPWE6	0.820	Valid
	NPWE7	0.791	Valid
	NPWE8	0.843	Valid
	NPWE9	0.794	Valid

<i>Worklife Balance</i>	WLB1	0.827	Valid
	WLB10	0.827	Valid
	WLB11	0.834	Valid
	WLB12	0.817	Valid
	WLB13	0.834	Valid
	WLB14	0.786	Valid
	WLB2	0.827	Valid
	WLB3	0.809	Valid
	WLB4	0.788	Valid
	WLB5	0.820	Valid
	WLB6	0.845	Valid
	WLB7	0.824	Valid
	WLB8	0.871	Valid
	WLB9	0.856	Valid
<i>Work Discipline</i>	WD1	0.816	Valid
	WD10	0.826	Valid
	WD11	0.854	Valid
	WD12	0.850	Valid
	WD13	0.808	Valid
	WD2	0.809	Valid
	WD3	0.816	Valid
	WD4	0.823	Valid
	WD5	0.769	Valid
	WD6	0.806	Valid
	WD7	0.813	Valid
	WD8	0.846	Valid
	WD9	0.820	Valid
<i>Turnover Intention Karyawan</i>	T11	0.801	Valid
	T12	0.817	Valid
	T13	0.764	Valid
	T14	0.807	Valid
	T15	0.780	Valid
	T16	0.780	Valid
	T17	0.779	Valid
	T18	0.724	Valid

B. Reliability Test

Table 2. Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha Test Results

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Non-Physical Work Environment (X1)	0.965	0.968	0.630
Worklife Balance (X2)	0.964	0.968	0.683
Work Discipline (X3)	0.959	0.964	0.672
Turnover Intention (Y)	0.909	0.926	0.612

C. Outer Model

Figure 1. Outer Model

D. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Table 3. Value of Determinant Coefficient (R Square)

Variable	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Turnover Intention (Y)	0.704	0.699

E. Hypothesis Test

Table 4. Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Relationship between Variables	Path Coefficient	t-statistic	P value	Result
H1	Non-physical work environment → employee turnover intention	-0.168	2.890	0.004	Accepted
H2	Worklife balance → employee turnover intention	-0.423	8.165	0.000	Accepted
H3	Work discipline → employee turnover intention	-0.323	6.841	0.000	Accepted

The results of the tests, as outlined in the table above, can be summarized as follows:

H1: Non-Physical Work Environment has a significant effect on Turnover Intention

Hypothesis testing for H1 aimed to determine whether the Non-Physical Work Environment impacts Turnover Intention. The analysis revealed a t-statistic value of 2.890, which is higher than the critical t-value of 1.653, and a significance value of 0.004, which is less than 0.05. These results indicate that the Non-Physical Work Environment significantly affects Turnover Intention, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (Ho) and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis (Ha). The original sample estimate is negative (-0.168), suggesting that a better Non-Physical Work Environment reduces Turnover Intention.

This supports previous research by Dian and Rayuwanto [32], which stated that relationships among employees and with supervisors are crucial factors in employee comfort at work. A conducive work environment enhances work motivation and ultimately improves job performance. A good work environment can reduce turnover intention, whereas a poor work environment can increase turnover intention. Yunita [33] also found that work environment negatively and significantly impacts turnover intention. This study confirms that a poor work environment at PT. YB Apparel Jaya Temanggung leads to an increase in turnover intention among production employees.

H2: Work-life balance has a significant effect on Turnover Intention

Hypothesis testing for H2 aimed to prove whether work-life balance affects employee Turnover Intention. The analysis produced a t-statistic value of 8.165, exceeding the critical t-value of 1.653, and a significance value of 0.000, which is smaller than 0.05. The results show that work-life balance significantly influences Turnover Intention, leading to the rejection of Ho and acceptance of Ha. The original sample estimate is negative (-0.423), indicating that better work-life balance lowers Turnover Intention.

This is in line with studies by Purwatiningsih and Sawitri [34], which found that work-life balance has a significant negative impact on turnover intention. When employees experience a high level of work-life balance, turnover intention within a company tends to be low. Koubova and Buchko [35] also stated that high work-life balance leads to a better life, which in turn enhances job performance and reduces turnover intention. It can be assumed that when employees are happy in their personal life, it directly translates into happiness at work [36]. Therefore, work-life balance is considered a key factor influencing employees' intention to leave the organization.

H3: Work discipline has a significant effect on employee Turnover Intention

Hypothesis testing for H3 aimed to verify whether work discipline impacts employee Turnover Intention. The analysis showed a t-statistic value of 6.841, higher than the critical t-value of 1.653, and a significance value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. The results indicate that work discipline significantly affects Turnover Intention, leading to the rejection of Ho and acceptance of Ha. The original sample estimate is negative (-0.323), meaning that improved work discipline leads to a reduction in Turnover Intention.

The results of this study support previous research, such as that conducted by Hutomo and Nawangsasi [37] and Yulianti et al. [38], which states that the higher the employees' awareness of adhering to all regulations, the more it reflects employee comfort, thereby preventing employees from leaving the company. Nuraldy et al. [9] also stated that the higher the employees' commitment to enforcing company regulations, the lower the employee turnover rate. This reflects employee comfort, which in turn prevents employees from leaving the company.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study and discussion, the research on the effect of non-physical work environment, work-life balance, and work discipline on employee turnover intention can be concluded as follows:

1. The non-physical work environment at PT Bhumi Phala Perkasa is categorized as good, with an average score of 779.3 based on descriptive analysis.
2. The work-life balance of employees at PT Bhumi Phala Perkasa is categorized as good, with an average score of 844.3 based on descriptive analysis.
3. The work discipline of employees at PT Bhumi Phala Perkasa is categorized as good, with an average score of 846.3 based on descriptive analysis.
4. Employee turnover intention at PT Bhumi Phala Perkasa is categorized as relatively low, with an average score of 681.4 based on descriptive analysis.
5. The non-physical work environment has a significant negative effect on turnover intention, as indicated by a p-value of 0.004, which is less than the alpha value of 0.05. The better the non-physical work environment, the lower the turnover intention.
6. Work-life balance has a significant negative effect on turnover intention, as indicated by a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the alpha value of 0.05. The better the work-life balance, the lower the turnover intention.
7. Work discipline has a significant negative effect on turnover intention, as indicated by a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the alpha value of 0.05. The better the work discipline, the lower the turnover intention.

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